

Polarographic Reduction of Some Potential Antineoplastic 5-Arylazopyrimidines

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The polarographic reduction of 2-amino-4, 6-dimethyl-5-arylazopyrimidines takes place at azo group in a single 2 electron diffusion controlled wave in the pH range 2.0-10.0. The waves are irreversible and the $E_{1/2}$ is dependent of pH and on concentration of depolarizer. The plots of $E_{1/2}$ vs pH are linear with slope 0.062-0.066 V/pH. A plausible mechanism has also been suggested on the basis of number of electrons involved in the reduction process and number of protons involved in the rate determining step. The effect of electron donating and electron withdrawing substituents has been interpreted in the terms of Hammett equation.

THE course of the polarographic reduction of pyrimidines and its derivatives has been studied extensively.¹⁻⁴ Nevertheless, most of the studies were restricted to comparison of half wave potential on the ease of reduction of $-C=N-$ group. A large number of 5-arylazopyrimidines, which have been synthesised by several manipulations to enhance the antitumour activity⁵ have attracted little attention. In the present studies various 2-amino-4, 6-dimethyl-5-arylazopyrimidines [A] have been investigated. The reduction in these compounds occurs at azo bond. The effect of substituents has also been compared by taking different alkyl groups at position 4 and 6 so as to include pyrimidines showing a wide variation in structure. A quantitative relationship between half-wave potential and Hammett substituent constant has also been established.

Experimental

All these pyrimidines (listed in table 1) were synthesised⁶ by the condensation of guanidine nitrate with properly substituted 2,3,4-pentanetrione-3-arylhydrazones. Two more compounds, viz., 2-amino-4-methyl-6-phenyl-5-phenylazopyrimidine and 2-amino-4,6-diphenyl-5-phenylazopyrimidine were also synthesised in order to investigate the effect of substituents at position 4 and 6. All the compounds were recrystallised in 50% ethanol. Stock solution ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$) of all the pyrimidines were prepared in methanol (AnalaR). Britton-Robinson Buffers⁷ in the pH range 2.0-10.0 were used. SCE was used as reference electrode.

Apparatus and Procedure

A Cambridge pen recording polarograph with capillary characteristic $2.0 \pm 0.05 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ S}^{-1/2}$ was used for recording the polarograms at $30 \pm 0.2^\circ$. The polarograms of all these pyrimidines were recorded after deaerating a mixture, composed of 2 ml compound, 0.5 ml gelatin (0.1%), 5.5 ml buffer and 2 ml methanol (which was necessary to keep these compounds in solution) with purified hydrogen gas. The procedure used for the coulometric determination of 'n', using a mercury pool cathode was the same as described earlier.⁸

Results and Discussion

All the pyrimidines studied show a single, 2 electron wave in the entire pH range. The height of the wave shows a linear dependence on concentration of depolarizer and $\sqrt{h}$. These facts confirm the diffusion controlled nature of the waves. The electrode process was found to be irreversible as the half-wave potential shifts towards more negative potential with increasing concentration of depolarizer. Irreversible nature of the waves is further confirmed by log plots.⁹ The half-wave potentials are dependent on pH and bear a linear relationship, the shift being 65-70 mv/pH (Table 1). The dependence of $E_{1/2}$ on pH indicates that prior to the first electron intake proton transfer takes place.

The value of P (number of protons involved per molecule of the reactant in the rate determining step) was determined using expressions

$$E_{1/4} - E_{3/4} = \frac{0.0517}{\alpha n_a}$$

$$\frac{dE_{1/2}}{dpH} = \frac{0.05915}{\alpha n_a} P$$

where αn_a is the product of transfer coefficient and number of electrons involved per molecule of the

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF SOME 5-ARYLAZOPYRIMIDINES AT pH 5.0, C=2.0 × 10⁻⁴ M

S. No.	R ₁	-E _{1/2} , V	id, μA	$\frac{dE_{1/2}}{dpH}$ mv/pH	αn	ΔE _{1/2} , V	P
1.	H	0.55	2.25	62	0.70	0.00	1.08
2.	2-Cl	0.56	1.50	66	0.76	-0.01	0.89
3.	3-Cl	0.56	2.00	64	0.76	-0.31	0.91
4.	4-Cl	0.50	1.50	66	0.84	+0.05	1.24
5.	3-Br	0.54	1.25	55	0.74	+0.01	0.95
6.	4-Br	0.49	1.50	53	0.72	+0.06	0.95
7.	2-CH ₃	0.65	1.46	66	0.76	-0.01	1.14
8.	3-CH ₃	0.59	1.46	64	0.87	-0.03	1.11
9.	4-CH ₃	0.51	1.68	66	0.78	+0.04	1.14
10.	2-OCH ₃	0.44	2.02	62	0.76	+0.11	0.89
11.	3-OCH ₃	0.52	2.12	64	0.87	+0.03	0.78
12.	4-OCH ₃	0.54	1.90	64	0.87	+0.01	1.11
13.	2-NO ₂	0.55	1.57	62	0.87	+0.00	1.08
14.	3-NO ₂	0.39	2.25	66	0.87	+0.16	0.94
15.	2-OC ₂ H ₅	0.50	2.10	64	0.87	+0.05	0.89
16.	2,5-(OCH ₃) ₂	0.52	1.57	66	0.84	+0.03	1.14
17.	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂	0.56	1.57	62	0.87	-0.01	1.08

reactant in the rate determining step of the electrode process. The values of P are summarized in Table 1.

The possible reduction sites in these compounds are cyclic -C=C-, -C=N- and exocyclic -N=N-. Out of these, the latter site is more susceptible to reduction as -C=N- and -C=C- requires higher potential for reduction. Since all the compounds reduced in a single, 2 electron wave the following general course for these azopyrimidines can be proposed :

A similar two electron mechanism for the reduction of azo compounds has also been proposed by Hillson¹⁰ and other workers¹¹⁻¹⁴. The above mechanism finds

support from the increase of E_{1/2} with pH as protons are involved.

For investigating the effect of methanol concentration, the parent compound, viz., 2-amino-4,6-dimethyl-5-phenylazopyrimidine is selected. It is observed that with increase in methanol concentration, the wave becomes distorted and the limiting current decreases. Similar behaviour has also been reported in other azo compounds¹⁵.

Effect of substituents

Because the value of $dE_{1/2}/dpH$ from E_{1/2} vs pH plots and degree of irreversibility (α) are practically constant for this series of compounds, the conditions of applying Hammett equation are fulfilled. The value of E_{1/2} are plotted against Hammett substituent constant (σ) in order to express the effect of substituents quantitatively. The values of σ_{p-X} are used from tables¹⁶. Figure 1 represents a linear plot of E_{1/2} vs σ. The plot shows that *m*- and *p*-derivatives, viz., 2-chloro, 2-ethoxy and 2-methoxy etc. show deviation. This can be accounted for on the basis of steric hindrance to coplanarity¹⁷. The value of specific reaction constant (ρ) is found to be 0.15 V which is comparable with the values reported¹⁶ for similar systems. The positive value of ρ indicates a nucleophilic mechanism (electron uptake as potential determining step).

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF 5-ARYLAZOPYRIMIDINE WITH DIFFERENT R₁ AND R₂ AT pH 5.0 AND C=2.0×10⁻⁴M.

R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	-E _{1/2} V	ΔE _{1/2} , V	id, μA	$\frac{dE_{1/2}}{dpH}$, mv/pH	αn	P
H	CH ₃	CH ₃	0.55	0.00	2.25	62	0.70	1.08
H	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	0.50	0.05	1.12	62	0.76	0.89
H	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	0.70	-0.15	2.35	66	0.84	0.94

Fig. 1 : Dependence of half wave potential of 2-amino-4,6-dimethyl-5-arylazopyrimidines on Hammett substituent constant in B.R. Buffer pH=5.0.

The negative value of polarographic ortho shift (Δ_o) determined by the expression

$$\Delta_o = (E_{1/2})_{o-X} - (E_{1/2})_{p-X}$$

for chloro and methyl groups showed that ortho derivatives are reduced at more negative potential corresponding to their p-derivatives. It has been reported that from the point of view of additivity of structural effects¹⁸⁻¹⁹ the data precise to 0.01V can be considered as additive. In the series studied, it was found that 2,5-dimethyl derivative showed additive nature whereas 2,5-dimethoxy did not follow it. The difference in behaviour may be due to the bulkiness of methoxy group.

An interesting behaviour is observed on replacing methyl groups of pyrimidine ring by phenyl groups. In the case of 2-amino-4-methyl-6-phenyl-5-phenylazopyrimidine a shift of 0.05 V towards more positive potential was observed (Table 2). This can be explained on the basis of electron withdrawing nature of phenyl group which increases the electron density at N of the azo group. When both the methyl groups were replaced by phenyl groups an opposite behaviour was observed. This can be accounted for on the basis of steric hindrance of molecules which varies according to shape and size of the group²⁰. Thus the E_{1/2} of 2-amino-4,6-diphenyl-5-phenylazopyrimidine shifts towards more negative potential because the values of radius and steric factor (2.20 Å² and 0.80 respectively) for the

phenyl group are quite high as compared to methyl group.

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